

Again, no communication routes

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At the beginning of the second quarter of the 21st century, when the Internet is shaping new trade dynamics and geographical borders are giving way to information flows, Ecuador has not managed to consolidate a road network that connects its inhabitants.

The Pan-American Highway, which was conceived at the Fifth International Conference of the OAS in 1923, still has weak and intermittent stretches in rainy seasons, disconnecting the country from the continent.

Without a safe road network, it is not possible to supply families with goods and services on a regular basis, and costs increase.

The last Easter holiday, for example, there were long columns of vehicles at the exits and entrances to Loja, and there were probably some who suspended their journeys due to the poor state of the roads.

Among other issues, the media report on the urgency of maintaining and expanding highways, but this need is abandoned in favour of other immediate needs. In this scenario that privileges the urgent, delays, loss of jobs and opportunities are generated because people are deprived of their right to communicate.

One dimension of freedom of expression is to have real and direct means of communication, to have roads and bridges for citizens to circulate and to be able to speak and listen to each other. Often the use of speech is reduced to data, computer or mobile phone numbers, and the public spaces that are essential for transit are forgotten.

While the solutions are being found, the south is once again further south because there are no roads available for travel and dialogue with the rest of the nation and the world.